

Hydrocracking catalyst selection in Indian context

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Hydrocracking of paraffinic vacuum gas oil of Bombay High origin (the major source in India) has been performed in a rocking-type high-pressure batch reactor (in laboratory scale) using zeolite-X based catalyst, with different metal loadings. The effect of temperature, total pressure, initial hydrogen pressure and residence time on conversion, selectivity and product characteristics have been studied in each case. Finally, a suitable catalyst composition and process condition is suggested for maximum production of Middle Distillate at a reasonable cost.

Catalyst plays an important role in hydrocracking and proper balance of the acid sites and hydrogenation-dehydrogenation sites is very much essential to get the desired product selectivity at optimum process conditions. Noble-metal based catalysts and non-noble metal based catalysts are the two basic categories of hydrocracking catalysts since zeolites are proved to be the best one as cracking component of the hydrocracking catalyst. Among these, noble metal based catalysts having higher hydrogenation-dehydrogenation activity, are more costly as compared to non-noble metal based one. Further, surface area, pore size, pore volume distribution, acidity etc. of the catalyst concerned have a great influence on hydrocracking reactions and hence on product distribution. It is found that for a given surface area of the support and for the fixed composition of the catalyst, the activity per gm. of the catalyst, the selectivity and the stability will be increased by decreasing the particle diameter and increasing the pore volume, particularly in case of heavy feeds¹.

In the present study, nickel-exchanged molecular sieve 13X as the non-noble metal based catalyst and palladium-exchanged molecular sieve 13X as the noble metal based catalyst have been tested for the variation in the following process parameters using paraffinic vacuum gas oil (VGO) of Bombay High origin as feedstock : temp. 598–748 K; total pressure, 3.5–8.5 Mpa; initial pressure of H₂, 3.5–6.5 Mpa; residence time, 7–60 min.

Results and Discussion

The vacuum gas oil feedstock had the following characteristics : boiling range, 643–823 K; sp. gr. (288.5 K), 0.8769; viscosity (310.8 K) (ASTM D445-83), 30.93; C-residue (Ramsbottom; ASTM D524-81), 0.4 wt%; total S (ASTM D129-64), 0.3 wt.%; N, 0.05 wt%; aromatic content, 29.3 wt.%; saturates content, 68.9 wt.% : C_N 15.2%, C_p 84.8%; pour point, 321 K.

Fig. 1 Schematic flow diagram of the experimental set up

The characteristics of NiX and PdX catalysts are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of catalysts

Parameter	NiX	PdX			
Metal content, wt%	2.5	0.46			
Sp surface area, m ² g ⁻¹	289.25	359.42			
Total pore volume, ml g ⁻¹	0.769	0.624			
Porosity, ml/100 ml	71.1	59.7			
Average pore radius, Å ^a	53.2	34.7			
Surface acidity, mg g ⁻¹	0.90	0.49			
Pore size distribution, % by volume (radius Å)					
	NiX	PdX	NiX	PdX	
4–15	0.6	13.6	200–300	0.1	2.4
15–30	7.4	4.2	300–400	1.0	1.8
30–60	6.4	6.0	400–500	0.5	1.8
60–100	3.4	4.2	>500	76.7	61.8
100–200	3.9	4.2			

^aAverage pore radius, $r_p = 2V/S$, where V = pore volume, ml g⁻¹ and S = sp surface area, m² g⁻¹

Effect of temperature : The data presented in Table 2 show that PdX catalyst is more effective at lower temperature range while NiX catalyst is effective at higher temperature range. At the highest temperature studied (748 K) NiX catalyst results in 5% more conversion than PdX catalyst. All these phenomenon are the result of higher cracking

Effect of total pressure : Variation in total pressure (Table 3) shows that, it has significant effect on NiX catalyst system as compared to PdX catalyst system, and NiX catalyst ultimately gives higher conversion. This can be explained on the basis of the intrinsic property of nickel and palladium, i.e. both of them absorbs hydrogen readily but the

Table 2. Effect of temperature

Total pressure = 3.55 Mpa, residence time = 15 min, initial pressure of H₂ = 3.55 Mpa

Parameter	NiX				PdX		
	648	698	723	748	698	723	748 K
(a) Yield, wt% of feed							
Gas	10.5	28.8	29.2	32.2	30.6	30.0	32.8
Lt distillate (IBP-423 K)	5.0	6.8	7.3	23.4	19.0	19.3	20.6
Mid distillate (423-573 K)	3.0	11.4	35.3	26.7	31.5	32.1	24.9
Hvy distillate (>573 K)	80.0	45.8	22.2	5.6	11.3	13.0	10.1
(b) % Conversion	small	47.4	70.2	82.4	81.5	81.4	78.3
(c) Selectivity for MD	-	24.1	47.4	32.1	38.7	39.4	31.8
(d) Amount of coke and tar, g	-	17.0	18.9	30.0	18.0	14.0	29.0
(e) Properties of liquid product							
Sp gr (288.5 K)	-	0.865	0.866	0.808	0.776	0.802	0.836
Viscosity (310.8 K), cSt		8.2	3.5	0.99	4.6	5.1	3.8

activity of the NiX catalyst which is more pronounced as the temperature is increased. It is also supported by significant increase in severity to gas and light distillate with simultaneous increase in coke deposit on the catalyst surface and consequent decrease in specific gravity and viscosity of the liquid hydrocracked product.

Hence, PdX catalyst can be effectively used for gasoline manufacture at low temperature. On the other hand, NiX catalyst is suitable for middle distillate manufacture at medium temperature level around 723 K.

rate of diffusion of hydrogen through nickel is slower than that through palladium. Again, thermodynamically, high pressure suppresses cracking reactions. These facts lead to decrease in conversion for NiX catalyst at higher pressure range. In case of PdX catalyst, cracking and hydrogenation both occur simultaneously thus maintaining the cracking sites clean for efficient operation. Increase in pressure, although leads to increased rate of diffusion of hydrogen through palladium, yet the advantage is offset by suppression of cracking at higher pressure. These, as a whole, maintain the

Table 3. Effect of total pressure

Temp = 723 K, residence time = 15 min, initial pressure of H₂ = 3.55 MPa

Parameter	NiX					PdX			
	3.55	4.93	5.62	6.99	8.38	3.55	4.93	6.31	7.34 Mpa
(a) Yield, wt% of feed									
Gas	29.2	21.4	28.0	43.6	30.4	30.0	29.2	30.4	28.8
Lt distillate	7.3	22.6	18.3	18.4	14.3	19.3	15.3	13.0	20.8
Mid distillate	33.3	35.6	41.2	24.5	33.8	32.1	37.2	36.3	33.7
Hvy distillate	22.2	8.0	7.2	9.5	17.0	13.0	15.2	17.1	12.8
(b) % Conversion	70.2	80.0	87.6	86.5	78.6	81.4	81.2	79.7	83.6
(c) Selectivity for MD	47.4	44.5	47.0	28.3	43.9	39.4	45.8	45.5	40.3
(d) Amt of coke and tar, g	18.9	30.0	13.0	10.0	11.0	14.0	9.0	8.0	9.0
(e) Properties of liquid product									
Sp gr (288.5 K)	0.866	0.775	0.796	0.815	0.840	0.803	0.841	0.950	0.870
Viscosity at 310.8 K, cSt	3.50	1.60	1.16	1.21	1.44	5.10	5.40	6.10	5.57

conversion at almost constant value for PdX catalyst.

Regarding product distribution, selectivity for MD is greater as compared to LD for both the catalysts. But comparable selectivity data, around 6.99 MPa, for NiX catalyst lead to the conclusion that it can be more efficiently used for gasoline manufacture at the pressure level mentioned as compared to PdX catalyst, by adjusting other variables. Thus, combining temperature and total pressure effect, it can be suggested that it is better to use PdX catalyst at low temperature for gasoline manufacture (at low pressure also) than to use NiX catalyst at high temperature and high pressure, considering the economics of the process.

Effect of initial pressure of hydrogen : Study of hydrogen initial pressure variation (Table 4) reveals that conversion decreases steadily with NiX catalyst while it increases

it is at higher hydrogen initial pressure level with simultaneous coke deposition, hence not favorable from economic point of view.

Effect of residence time : The data presented in Table 5 show that conversion first increases with increasing residence time and then decreases with further increase in residence time due to onset of secondary reactions. Both the catalysts give almost identical value of 86–87% for maximum conversion, but at different residence time. NiX requires less time than PdX to achieve the same conversion level, which may be due to its greater cracking activity. As regards the yield and selectivity of MD, both NiX and PdX behave in the same manner. But as gasoline is concerned, yield is almost constant for NiX catalyst, while it decreases at first then increases with increase in residence time for

Table 4. Effect of initial pressure of hydrogen*

Temp = 723 K, residence time 15 min

Parameter	NiX ^a			PdX ^b		
	3 55	4 24	4 93	3 55	4 24	4 93 Mpa
(a) Yield, wt% of feed						
Gas	28 0	35 2	27 2	29 2	36 9	38 2
Lt distillate	18 3	20 1	18 2	15 3	17 6	18 4
Mid distillate	41 2	24 7	30 5	37 2	31 5	32 3
Hvy distillate	7 2	12 3	16 6	15 2	10 3	8 4
(b) % Conversion	87 6	80 1	75 8	81 2	86 5	89 2
(c) Selectivity for MD	47 0	30 8	40 2	45 8	36 4	36 2
(d) Amount of coke and tar, g	13 0	19 0	19 0	9 0	8 0	6 0
(e) Properties of liquid product						
Sp gr (288 5 K)	0 796	0 859	0 801	0 841	0 899	0 846
Viscosity (310 8 K), cSt	1 16	1 47	1 37	5 4	5 8	5 45

*Total pressure ^a5 62, ^b4 93 Mpa

for PdX catalyst with increase in initial pressure of hydrogen. The hydrogenation effect of PdX catalyst is more favoured by increasing initial as well as partial pressure of hydrogen, thus favouring the hydrocracking reactions as a whole. But due to slower diffusion of hydrogen through nickel, H₂-availability for hydrocracking over NiX catalyst is not adequate, hence conversion decreases with increase in hydrogen initial pressure. Yield and selectivity data show that for MD, these are highest at low hydrogen initial pressure which then decreases as pressure is increased further; although the overall yield is highest for NiX catalyst. But for LD, yield increases at first and then decreases with increase in initial pressure of hydrogen for NiX catalyst, while it remains almost constant for PdX catalyst. In this case also, PdX catalyst is more suitable for gasoline manufacture since NiX catalyst although results in higher yield but

PdX catalyst. This is also due to the predominant hydrogenation activity of the PdX catalyst which prevents the secondary polymerization reactions to occur. Hydrogenation also helps in cracking heavy refractory molecules to middle one and then to lower one yielding more gasoline as time is increased but with less coke formation. Hence PdX catalyst can be selectively used for gasoline manufacture.

It may, therefore, be concluded that in upgrading vacuum gas oil of paraffinic nature through hydrocracking, nickel-exchanged zeolite is the suitable catalysts, i.e. for maximum production of MD, while palladium-exchanged one is more suitable for gasoline production. It is also evident from literature that the commonly used hydrogenating components, i.e. nickel and tungsten in combination, on different supports, are most suitable for converting gas oil to middle distillate².

Table 5. Effect of residence time*

Temp = 723 K, initial pressure of H₂ = 3.55 MPa

Parameter	NiX ^a				PdX ^b			
	7	15	30	60	7	15	30	60
(a) Yield, wt% of feed								
Gas	31.7	28.0	21.6	23.7	33.2	29.2	31.6	29.1
Lt distillate	18.1	18.3	17.4	18.4	20.2	15.2	22.4	23.8
Mid distillate	28.0	41.2	37.2	29.0	23.0	37.2	32.7	24.6
Hvy distillate	16.9	7.2	13.8	17.6	19.0	15.2	8.0	14.4
(b) % Conversion	78.3	87.6	76.2	71.2	76.6	81.2	86.4	78.0
(c) Selectivity for MD	35.8	47.0	48.8	40.7	30.0	45.8	37.8	31.5
(d) Amount of coke and tar, g	12.0	13.0	25.0	28.0	11.0	9.0	14.0	20.0
(e) Properties of liquid product								
Sp gr (288.5 K)	0.840	0.796	0.728	0.86	0.829	0.841	0.827	0.899
Viscosity (310.8 K), cSt	1.64	1.16	1.49	1.21	5.19	5.1	5.17	5.8

*Total pressure ^a5.62, ^b4.93 Mpa

On the basis of physicochemical characteristics of the two catalysts studied, it is also established that, besides surface area and acidity, pore size and pore volume distribution has a strong influence on product selectivity. Thus, NiX possessing lower surface area, results in greater conversion as compared to PdX, due to its higher porosity and total pore volume, thus enabling access of more reactant molecules to the active sites. Pore size distribution data reveal that greater pores in the higher pore diameter region (500–75000 Å) for NiX catalysts also enable to accommodate larger feed molecules of VGO thus resulting in greater conversion. Lower number of pores in the diameter region less than 500 Å in NiX catalysts, also does not allow the reaction intermediates to crack further, instead the intermediates transform into molecules in the MD region, thus increasing the yield of MD as compared to gasoline or lighter.

Hence comparatively cheaper nickel-based catalysts can be successfully adopted for Indian hydrocracking units with available indigenous paraffinic feedstocks to meet the growing challenge of middle distillate.

Experimental

Vacuum Gas Oil of Bombay High origin was used as feedstock. Metal-exchanged (nickel and palladium) molecular sieve 13X (ACC Ltd.) in the form of 1.5 mm diameter cylindrical extrudates was used.

A high pressure batch autoclave (1 dm³) made of S.S. 316 of rocking type was used for the hydrocracking reac-

tion. The details of the reactor is described elsewhere³.

The catalyst preparation involved only metal impregnation on the pre-formed support and it was done in the most conventional way of ion-exchanging, first with ammonium ions followed by required metal ions (Ni and Pd). The process is described in details elsewhere⁴.

Procedure: The whole set-up of the experimental assembly is shown in Fig. 1. The autoclave was first charged with requisite amount of feed and catalyst (feed : catalyst ratio = 10 : 1, w/w) and placed in position. Requisite amount of gas (hydrogen and/or nitrogen) was then charged (after purging the air) till the attainment of the desired initial pressure. It was then heated upto the required temperature when rocking started and continued throughout the residence time studied (the time interval between attainment of temperature and release). Hot release of the gas and vapour was then done, the condensed liquid product collected and fractionated into different fractions and analysed (ASTM methods). The coke deposited on the spent catalyst left in the reactor was determined by weighing.

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